

REPRESENTATION OF PERSONAL NAMES IN THESAURUSES

¹Kholmurodova I.A., ²Askarov R.A.

^{1,2}First-year Master's Students in Computational Linguistics, National University of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14580773>

Abstract. *This article explores the meanings and types of the term thesaurus and how personal name units are represented within thesauruses, illustrated with examples. The linguistic significance and practical application of personal name thesauruses are discussed in detail. Additionally, the article highlights research conducted in Uzbekistan and abroad on thesauruses, with a focus on the scientific contributions of international scholars. Information about the WordNet thesaurus is also provided. Moreover, examples of personal name thesaurus entries are given, including synonyms, antonyms, and explanations for certain personal name units.*

Keywords: *hyponym, hypernym, personal name thesauruses, linguistic approaches, thesaurus development, WordNet thesaurus.*

Introduction

In recent years, increasing attention has been given to computational linguistics as a scientific and practical field that encompasses knowledge about methods for extracting information from texts, searching and indexing documents based on their content, and linguistic topics, including the development of speech. There is a growing demand for systematized, automated, and easily accessible knowledge in computational linguistics, including adapting its terminology, enhancing the effectiveness of education, indexing related publications, and simplifying the application of knowledge in this field.

Computational linguistics is one of the emerging disciplines in Uzbek linguistics. Currently, various research initiatives are emerging in Uzbek computational linguistics. However, the field faces several challenges and unresolved issues. Among these is the task of compiling and explaining computational linguistics terminology, establishing computational lexicography, creating Uzbek-language computational dictionaries, and developing thesauruses as essential knowledge databases [3].

The creation of a thesaurus in Uzbek is considered one of the significant achievements in linguistics, aligned with the globalization process. Uzbek linguistics is also witnessing research in computational lexicography. However, unveiling a thesaurus for every word in Uzbek is a challenging task. Consequently, research has primarily focused on verbs, which form the core of sentences and express the essence of ideas.

In Uzbekistan, significant scholarly work has been carried out on thesauruses. For example, Professor Nilufar Abdurakhmonova's article *"The Representation of Lexical Units in Creating Uzbek Language Thesaurus"* discusses the importance of creating thesauruses, the methods used by researchers, and their significance. The article emphasizes the critical use of synonyms, antonyms, homonyms, and taxonomic relationships in Uzbek language.

Another notable work, *"The Conceptual Importance of Creating a Thesaurus Using a Corpus,"* explores the role of corpus linguistics in thesaurus creation and its application to Uzbek language. These studies aim to develop and refine Uzbek-language thesauruses by addressing

lexical representation, interrelations among lexical units, and the application of corpus linguistics approaches.

Verb Forms and Proper Nouns in Linguistics: Importance and Analysis

Proper nouns, just as verb forms are essential in the grammar of any language, hold a significant place in linguistics. These are the linguistic units that represent individuals or their social characteristics and also serve as key elements that link one person with others. Proper nouns play a critical role not only in communication but also in shaping personal and social identities. Thesauruses, including synonym and antonym dictionaries, assist in using proper nouns, thereby enhancing their communicative function.

Thesauruses such as WordNet, developed by various countries, have been successfully used in natural language processing tasks. The construction and organization of lexical information in thesaurus form have been thoroughly described in the research of N.V. Lukashevich. The structure, principles of operation, and capabilities of thesaurus databases like WordNet hold significant academic and practical value. In the field of computational linguistics, thesaurus dictionaries are essential sources, not only for philologists but also for professionals in information technology.

Analysis of Literature on the Subject

In his book *“Тезаурусы в задачах информационного поиска”* (Thesauruses in Information Retrieval Tasks), Russian scholar N.V. Lukashevich provides comprehensive information on how thesauruses should be structured, the standards for their creation, and the importance of thesaurus construction. This book can serve as a foundation for any work related to thesauruses. M. Narziyeva's article *“The Component Analysis of Kinship Nouns”* contributed to fully explaining proper nouns. Demand for research in thesaurus creation is increasing year by year, as thesauruses provide more precise meanings of words in context.

Research Methodology

Various global studies have been conducted regarding the thesaurus concept and its further development. Thesaurus dictionaries (such as WordNet and pyTe3) have been developed in countries like the United States and Russia. However, a thesaurus for proper nouns in Uzbek language has not yet been compiled. Based on the aforementioned sources, this article discusses this research.

Analysis and Results

Today, terms like taxonomy, thesaurus, and ontology are widely used. Taxonomy refers to a specialized vocabulary built on semantic relationships such as ancestor-descendant (parent-child) or whole-part, creating a hierarchical structure. A thesaurus, however, is a more expansive type of controlled vocabulary, encompassing internal relationships among larger words, and includes both hierarchical and equivalent relationships.

The term "thesaurus" (from the Greek "thesauros," meaning treasure) is often noted in sources, though Douglas Harper suggests that the term may have originated from the Greek verb meaning "to place" or "to position." According to Robert Beekes, the term was first used as a dictionary or encyclopedia between the 16th and 19th centuries (e.g., "Thesaurus Linguae Latinae" in 1532 and "Thesaurus Linguae Graecae" in 1572).

Thesauruses are dictionaries that organize words and phrases into synonym and antonym categories. A thesaurus provides a standardized vocabulary set built around key concepts, showing semantic relationships among the words. It plays a significant role in linguistics and expands

vocabulary. Words within a thesaurus are organized by thematic categories, depending on the field in which they are used.

A.N. Baranov and D.O. Dobrovolskiy define a thesaurus in the preface to "*От редакции*" (From the Editorial Board) as "a dictionary that differs from others (such as explanatory or bilingual dictionaries) in its method of organizing linguistic material." In a thesaurus, linguistic units are not listed alphabetically as in regular dictionaries but are grouped by meaning.

L.V. Shcherba, in his article "*Опыт теории общей лексикографии*" (Experience in General Lexicography Theory), mentions that modern thesauruses are often associated with *Thesaurus Linguae Latinae* and notes that they include all significant words in a language, with examples from texts where these words appear. He emphasizes that the motivation for creating a thesaurus stems from scientific and linguistic interests. While traditional dictionaries reflect the linguistic path of a particular language, a thesaurus organizes "linguistic material" based on the objective speech activity of a community, which he argues is the only linguistic truth in practice.

Thus, the thesaurus, by organizing words according to meaning rather than alphabetical order, offers a more nuanced and effective way of understanding and applying language.

Ways and Methods of Describing and Naming a Person in Uzbek

In Uzbek, the description and naming of a person have been studied in great detail, with various methods for identifying individuals based on different characteristics. Below are some of the common ways of naming a person in Uzbek language:

By Gender: erkak-ayol (man-woman), bobo-kampir (grandfather-grandmother), qiz-o'g'il (girl-boy).

By Kinship: ota-ona (father-mother), tog'a-amma (uncle-aunt).

By Age: ninni, chaqaloq, go'dak (infant, baby, child), bola, yigit (boy, young man).

By Nationality: o'zbek, tojik, qirg'iz, rus (Uzbek, Tajik, Kyrgyz, Russian).

By Place of Residence: buxorolik, samarqandlik, xorazmlik, navoiylik (from Bukhara, Samarkand, Khorezm, Navoi).

By Profession: ovchi (hunter), baliqchi (fisherman), traktorchi (tractor driver).

By Body Structure: baqaloq, novcha, pakana (short, thin, small).

By Behavior: ayyor, badjahl, xushfe'l (cunning, bad-tempered, good-natured).

By Specific Characteristics: shalpanquloq (ears stuck out).

By Physical Disability: cho'loq (crippled), ko'r (blind), soqov (mute), gung (deaf), duduq (stutter).

By Behavior: qo'rs (arrogant), o'jar (stubborn), muloyim (gentle).

While these are just a few examples, they illustrate the various linguistic tools and methods available for naming individuals in Uzbek. These naming methods help to express social, physical, and behavioral characteristics of people.

In the context of thesauruses, certain proper nouns are included, and words that are semantically related or closely connected are grouped. Thesauruses are closely related to monolingual dictionaries that define the main parameters of words. For example, S.I. Ozhegov's dictionary of Russian language can be considered an example of this.

In a thesaurus, semantic relationships between words are represented through antonyms, synonyms, hyponyms, hypernyms, and groups. Let's examine these connections in the context of a thesaurus for proper nouns:

Synonyms: Words with similar meanings but different forms, e.g., *chiroyli* (beautiful) = *go‘zal* (beautiful).

In the thesaurus of proper nouns:

Shifokor (doctor) = *tabib* (physician) = *doktor* (doctor).

Antonyms: Words with opposite meanings, e.g., *yaxshi* (good) = *yomon* (bad).

In the thesaurus of proper nouns:

Kasal (sick) = *sog‘lom* (healthy).

Hyponyms: Specific terms that belong to a general category, e.g., *zobit* (officer) as a hyponym of *harbiy* (military).

In the thesaurus of proper nouns:

Hamshira (nurse) = *giponim* (specific to nursing).

Vrach (doctor) = *giponim* (specific to medicine).

Ukol (injection) = *dori* (medicine) = *giponim* (related to treatment).

Hypernyms: General terms that encompass a range of specific terms, e.g., a doctor as a hypernym that includes various specialties like cardiologist, surgeon, etc.

In the thesaurus of proper nouns:

A doctor who is skilled in multiple aspects of treatment can be considered a general term under the hypernym "*malakali shifokor*" (skilled doctor), which encapsulates various specialized knowledge and techniques.

These semantic relationships enhance the depth and utility of a thesaurus, making it an essential tool for understanding the nuances of proper noun usage in the language.

Personal Nouns

Personal nouns are names that refer to individual people or groups of people. They often include the social, cultural, and psychological characteristics of a person. Personal nouns enrich the language and play an important role in social communication. They are often divided into groups based on social, cultural, or historical contexts.

The classification in thesauruses helps understand the usage of personal nouns. Through the representation of personal nouns in thesauruses:

It enriches the language by enabling readers and writers to discover new words and synonyms.

It makes it easier to understand how personal nouns are used in various contexts by systematizing information.

It helps eliminate interlingual differences and promotes social communication.

By studying personal nouns, they are explored as research objects in various contemporary fields of linguistics, and the creation of their thesaurus helps deeply analyze their scientific essence. For example, cognitive linguistics protects personal nouns from a psychological and social perspective.

Conclusion: The representation of personal nouns in thesauruses holds significant importance in linguistics and communication. They enrich the language, systematize information, and foster social communication. Additionally, studying and analyzing personal nouns opens up new avenues for research in the fields of linguistics and philology. Thesauruses serve as essential tools for using personal nouns effectively and purposefully, enhancing their communicative function. In the field of computer linguistics, thesaurus dictionaries are important resources not only for philologists but also for information technology professionals.

Synonymy and Antonymy in the Thesaurus of Personal Nouns

Personal nouns	Synonyms	Antonyms	Comment
friend	Close friend, dear, brother	Enemy	trusted person or close individual
Sly	deceiver	Simple	description given to a person's character
Poor	Needy	Wealthy	the social status of a person
Angry	Nervous	Kind	a person who deviates from values, with bad habits or behaviors
Stubborn	Headstrong, wild	believer, capable, gentle	a description based on a person's behavior
Physician	Doctor	-	a specialist who deals with the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of diseases
outstanding	Knowledgeable	Ignorant	Description given to a person for evaluating knowledge
King	Monarch, ruler	beggar	A person who governs or controls a country
Tailor	Dressmaker	-	Skilled in sewing clothes or embroidery
Brave	Hero, courageous, fearless, brave.	Coward, dishonorable	A person who is always ready to help and is not afraid of anything

These studies help deepen the understanding of the social, cultural, and historical significance of personal nouns, as well as pave the way for new scientific research.

REFERENCES

- Narziyeva M. "The Component Analysis of Kinship Names" // Uzbek Language and Literature, 1986, Issue 5. - p.47-48.
- Lukashevich N. "Thesauruses in Information Retrieval Tasks," 2011. p.20-50.
- Khomonova Z. "Computer Linguistics," Tashkent-2020, Asian Book House, p.81-103.
- Abdurahmonova N. "Computer Linguistics Textbook" – Tashkent: Nodirabegim, 2021, p.171.
- Nizomova Z. "Principles of Creating Thesaurus Dictionaries," International Scientific-Practical Conference "Computer Linguistics: Problems, Solutions, Prospects," Tashkent-2022, p.443-453.
- Qilichev B. "Onomastics Study Guide" – Bukhara: 2023, p.12-13.
- Shcherba L. "Experience of General Lexicography Theory," 1940. <https://www.ruthenia.ru/apr/textes/sherba/sherba9.htm>
- Dobrovolsky V. "From the Editorial; From the Compiler," S. Baranova. - Moscow, 1965. p.4-6.
- San'atbek M., Mirsaid A., & Nilufar A. (2018). "Modeling WordNet Type Thesaurus for Uzbek Language Semantic Dictionary," International Journal of Systems Engineering, 2(1), 26.

10. Nilufar A., & Gulruhsor X. (2024). "Standards in Creating an Uzbek Language Thesaurus," *Contemporary Technologies of Computational Linguistics*, 2(22.04), 464-469.
11. Nilufar A., & Gulruhsor X. (2024, May). "Expression of Lexical Units in the Creation of an Uzbek Language Thesaurus," In *Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 10, pp. 186-192).
12. Abdurakhmonova N., & Latipova G. "Ontological Syntactic Structures of the Uzbek Language for Corpus Analysis," *Materials of the International Scientific-Theoretical Conference*, p.449.
13. <https://www.uza.uz>